

Mixed Precision Multigrid Methods on Hybrid Tetrahedral Grids

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²Chair for System Simulation (LSS)

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- 1. Low Precision**
 - 2. Mixed Precision**
 - 3. Numerical Experiment**
 - 4. Runtime Investigation**
 - 5. Conclusion**

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Problem

$$Au = f$$

Reducing

Memory size

Runtime

Energy Consumption

Compatibility problems for float16

- Compiler → Only with CXX23 and GCC13
- MPI → Requires own definition
- Hardware → Sapphire Rapid Generation from Intel

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Error estimate

$$e_{\text{tot}} \leq e_{\text{disc}} + e_{\text{quant}} + e_{\text{solver}}$$

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For a 2. order PDE in L^2 -norm:

	\mathbb{P}_1	\mathbb{P}_2
e_{disc}	$\mathcal{O}(h^2)$	$\mathcal{O}(h^3)$

Strand et al. “An analysis of the finite element method” 2014

Smooth 2D Poisson Problem using Fixed Precision

Iterative Refinement

```
1 IR( $\dot{A}$ ,  $\bar{A}$ ,  $u$ ,  $f$ ):  
2 |  $\bar{r} = f - \bar{A} u$   
3 |  $\bar{r} = \text{cast}(\dot{r}, \dot{\epsilon})$   
4 |  $\text{initZero}(\dot{e}, \dot{\epsilon})$   
5 | loop  $i$  from 1 to  $M$   
6 | |  $\text{solve}(\dot{A} \dot{e}, \dot{r})$   
7 |  $e = \text{cast}(\dot{e}, \epsilon)$   
8 |  $u = u - e$ 
```

For a 2. order PDE in L^2 -norm:

\mathbb{P}_1

\mathbb{P}_2

$\mathcal{O}(h^3)$

$\mathcal{O}(h^4)$

$\mathcal{O}(h)$

$\mathcal{O}(h)$

$$\bar{r} = \bar{A}\bar{u} - \bar{f} \quad \text{OR} \quad \dot{A}\dot{e} = \dot{r}$$

□ Functions u, f, e, r

Storage of Values on the Grid

Descriptions of Vec-Vec operations

□ Operator A

Descriptions of Mat-Vec operations

Functions in target precision

- Arbitrary function precision → Templating \mathbb{P}_1 function classes
- Casting between types → Exists for \mathbb{P}_1

Operator in target precision

- Mat-Vec operations → Typing for code generator HOG
→ Constant casting for generation

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Smooth 3D Poisson Problem using Mixed Precision

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Time to Solution

1. Ord. Chebyshev Smoother ($l = 9$)

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$$x^{(n+1)} = x^{(n)} + \omega D^{-1} (b - \underbrace{Ax^{(n)}}_{\text{apply}})_{\text{assign}}_{\text{mult}}_{\text{assign}}$$

1. Ord. Chebyshev Smoother ($l = 9$)

$$x^{(n+1)} = x^{(n)} + \underline{\omega} D^{-1} (b - \underbrace{Ax^{(n)}}_{\text{apply}})_{\text{assign}}_{\text{mult}}_{\text{assign}}$$

apply of Cheby ($l = 9$)

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Conclusion

- Mixed Precision implemented for HyTeg works for \mathbb{P}_1 elements
- Float32 is applicable by itself up to level 7 (8.48×10^6 DoFs)
- IR increases the range for accurate applicability for float32
- Float16 works in general up to level 3 (2.45×10^3 DoFs)
BUT no advantage using IR, as of now
- MP yields potential for scientific computations
Still room for performance improvements in HyTeG

Future Work

- Investigation of named performance issue “fixes”
- Extending MP support for further function spaces
- Investigation of solver modifications to utilize float16
- Scaling benchmarks with IR
- Porting HyTeG kernels to GPUs

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2. Kohl Nils et al., Textbook Efficiency: Massively Parallel Matrix-Free Multigrid for the Stokes System, 2022
3. Fabian Böhm et al., Code Generation and Performance Engineering for Matrix-Free Finite Element Methods on Hybrid Tetrahedral Grids, 2024
4. Strand Gilbert et al., An analysis of the finite element method, 1973
5. Higham Nicholas, Accuracy and stability of numerical algorithms, 2002
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7. Ofenbeck Georg et al., Applying the roofline model, 2014

Float16 Benchmark Kernel

$$r[i] = v[i] + vv[i]; \quad N = 10^8$$

Fritz : Platinum 8470 core (Sapphire Rapid)

LSS CIP : Xeon E3 core

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla \phi = \int_{\Omega} f \phi$$

$$\Omega = [0, 1]^2$$

$$f = 0$$

$$u|_{\Gamma_D} = \sin(x) \sinh(y)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla \phi = \int_{\Omega} f \phi$$

$$\Omega = [0, 1]^3$$

$$f = \sin(2x) \sinh(y) \cosh(z)$$

$$u|_{\Gamma_D} = 0.5 \sin(2x) \sinh(y) \cosh(z)$$

Float16 Investigation

- $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\epsilon=fp_{32}}$: ○ lvl 2 ○ lvl 3 ○ lvl 4
- $IR_{\bar{\epsilon}=fp_{32}>\epsilon=fp_{16}}$: ★ lvl 2 ★ lvl 3 ★ lvl 4
- $GMG_{\bar{\epsilon}=\epsilon=fp_{16}}$: ◇ lvl 2 ◇ lvl 3 ◇ lvl 4

$$\text{solve} \left(\bar{A}_h \tilde{u}_h = \overline{\text{rhs}}_h ; IR_{\dot{\epsilon} \leq \bar{\epsilon}} ; e_{\text{tot}} \overset{!}{<} e_{\text{rel}} ; \|\cdot\|_{\tilde{l}^2} \right)$$

$$\Omega_l = [0, 1]^3 \quad l \in \{6, 7, 8, 9\} \quad \Omega_0 \rightarrow 24 \text{ macro-tets}$$

$$e_{\text{rel}} = 1.5 \times e_{\text{disc}}^{\text{GMG}_{fp64}}$$

$$IR : \quad \dot{\epsilon} = fp32 \quad \bar{\epsilon} = fp64 ; \quad N \in 1, 4$$

Runtimes for one V-cycle

Significand is the precision (i.e., only p from k)

sign exponent field trailing significand field

Epsilon

Error Explanation

$$e_{\text{tot}} \leq e_{\text{disc}} + e_{\text{solve}} + e_{\text{round}}$$

Error Explanation

$$e_{\text{tot}} \leq e_{\text{disc}} + e_{\text{rep}} + e_{\text{quant}} + e_{\text{it}} + e_{\text{op}}$$

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